

Formation Constants of the Chelates of 4-Nitro-Benzilidene-Ortho-Carboxy-aniline with Some Bivalent Metal Ions

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on metal chelates of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} with 4-nitro-benzilidene-ortho-carboxy-aniline. The dissociation constant (ρK_1) of the reagent and the formation constants of its metal chelates have been determined by Bjerrum's method at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and at ionic strength of 0.1 M, in 75:25 percent (v/v) dioxan : water medium.

LITERATURE survey indicates that no study of the stabilities of 4-Nitro-benzilidene-ortho-carboxy-aniline and its metal chelates has been carried out.

In the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 4-nitro-benzilidene-ortho-carboxy-aniline with some bivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 4-nitro-benzilidene ortho-carboxy-aniline was synthesised by dissolving 10 g of anthranilic acid in 75 ml of distilled benzene and to this was added equimolar quantity of 4-nitro-benzaldehyde. The mixture was refluxed for about two hours and then was allowed to cool when solid separated out and was removed by filtration and air dried. The product was repeatedly crystallised from benzene to get an analytically pure compound. (Observed m.p. 168° , Literature m.p. 167°)².

The dioxan used for the experimental work was purified by the method described by Vogel³. Distilled water required, was redistilled over alkaline potassium permanganate.

The medium of titration was 75:25% dioxan water (v/v) mixture. Sodium perchlorate was added to maintain a constant ionic strength (0.1 M). The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by bubbling nitrogen gas through the solutions. All the metal perchlorate solutions were prepared from salts of A.R. grade. The metal ion solutions were standardised complexometrically⁴ by EDTA titrations.

The Corning model 12, a precision research pH meter with a wide range glass electrode and a calomel reference electrode was used for the pH measurements. The meter has an arrangement for normal and expanded scale. The smallest scale division on the expanded scale is 0.005 pH unit.

The following solutions were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free sodium-hydroxide (1.04 M) solution.

- (1) 5 ml of (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 30 ml of dioxan.
- (2) 5 ml. of (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.
- (3) 5 ml of (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml of (0.008 M) metal salt solution in (0.16 M) HClO_4 + requisite amount of the reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL.

Results and Discussion

The reagent under investigation did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titration and by the absence of any significant drift in the pH even after one hour.

In the ligand it is the chelated carboxylic 'OH' group, which takes part in the complex formation and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. Since only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the total number of dissociable protons attached to each ligand molecule is one.

Fig. 1A.

Fig. 1B.

From the titration curves (Figs 1A & 1B) using the solutions (1) and (2), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings) were calculated, and the curve between 'B' and the corresponding $\bar{n}_A$ values was plotted. The formation curve extends over a range $0.41 < \bar{n}_A < 0.93$ and is wavelike. From this curve, the values of practical pK_{OH}^H was calculated which corresponds to 'B' value at $\bar{n}_A$ equal to 0.5. A plot of $\log [\bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A)]$ against 'B' was also drawn. From this curve the value of practical pK_{OH}^H was calculated. The two values agree quite well.

Fig. 2

From the titration curves of solutions (2) and (3), $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values obtained do not reach beyond 1.0 and hence $\log K_1$ values only could be determined by half integral and graphical methods. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of metal complexing equilibria (Fig. 2). From these formation curves the values of stability constants, $\log K_1$ were computed which correspond to pL values at $\bar{n}=0.5$.

A plot of $\log [\bar{n} / (1 - \bar{n})]$ against pL for the different metal systems was also drawn. From these curves the values of $\log K_1$ were evaluated. The values obtained by both the methods agree quite well.

The most representative values are recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE 1—PROTON-LEGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS.

t = 25°C		μ = 0.1 M			
Cations	H ⁺	Cu ²⁺	Co ²⁺	Ni ²⁺	Zn ²⁺
log K ₁	7.82	6.13	4.07	3.87	3.70

The order of stability of divalent metal complexes was found to be: Cu²⁺ > Co²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Zn²⁺

The reversal in the order of Ni and Co in the present investigation as compared to the order observed by Maley and Mellor⁵ may be attributed to the closeness of the values.

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